

Incentive to Marginalized Girls for Secondary Education: A Study of National Scheme of Incentive for Girls in Secondary Education

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Abstract

Education is the pre-eminent device for the socio-economic, political and cultural transformation. At all times society from different social backgrounds has been interested to undergo the avenues of knowledge. The need of women's education and its liberating power was needed much more to the Indian society due to redundant age old customs, 'superstitions' and rustic traditions of the past. Women's education in Independent India, though progressed at a low pace, unable to reach the target of fulfilling universality. The trials of making Indian women literate, seems to be an impeccable and uphill task as girls representing the socially challenged sections – landless agricultural labourers and unlettered masses, could not send their girls to schools due to obvious reasons. The State has organized a wide range of self-evolved strategies and transforming mechanisms for reaching the unreached girls largely to bring issues of women's education into public discourse through a number of incentives and self-developing programmes attempting and making a crucial paradigm shift from subalternity to social respectability. This paper focuses on the innovative and renovative scheme offered to the secondary school going girls belonging to the underprivileged sections by the government of India – National Scheme of Incentives for Girls Secondary Education (NSIGSE), for accessing, enhancing and retaining all school-going girls to successfully complete schooling and to make a better future. The paper analyzes systematically the scheme, implementation, impact and impression on the school life of girls in the secondary and higher secondary classes, leading into making some impressive hallmarks in the annals of education of girls in India.

Keywords Girl's Education, Marginalized, Incentive Scheme, Secondary Education.

Introduction

Education is very prominent to the human resources development and empowerment in the stages of growth of any nation. School education, as it is well known plays a major role in imparting basic knowledge, values, developing skills and in the process, increase the growth and productivity of the nation. While there are initiatives for providing elementary and secondary education, certain provisions are given by the government. In order to recuperate the school education system, new initiatives to be brought both by the centre and the states and also special attention needs to be given to see school education brighter and stronger.

True progress and advancement for any society is impossible if girls are excluded. The social and economic goals of the future depend heavily on the status of girls today. Girls' education yields some of the highest returns of all investment in development benefitting individuals, families, and society as a whole. Almost every conceivable strategy and approach has been covered in policy documents of the Government of India. All policy documents recognize that the first stumbling block is poverty, and that women from poor communities, especially in rural areas need special attention. The second stumbling block is social status, especially when considering children from disadvantaged communities, most specifically, Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, some minority groups and so on. While affirmative action in the form of reservation of jobs and places in institutions of higher learning have been provided, there is irrefutable evidence to show that the elementary and secondary levels are the badly-affected sectors. It has been observed that

children belong to Below Poverty Line (BPL) families do not have access to secondary education at large.

Education of girls has been identified a high priority with the Government of India. The commitment to provide free and compulsory education to all children in the 6-14 years age group is now a 'fundamental right' of every child in India after the passing of the Constitution (86th Amendment) Act in December 2002. Reaching out to the girl child is central to the efforts to universalize elementary education. Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, or 'Education for All' programme recognizes that ensuring girl's education requires changes not only in the education system but also in societal norms and attitudes.

Considering all these factors, the Government of India, through its Ministry of Education, Government of India brings out some of the schemes for the girl students, who are coming from the poor and poverty-ridden families. Out of many such schemes, one is, National Scheme of Incentive to Girls for Secondary Education (NSIGSE), launched and implemented in all States in our country since 2008.

Aim of study

The objective of this paper is to analyze and understand how far this incentive scheme, National Scheme of Incentive for Girls in secondary Education (NSIGSE) benefits monetarily, such as the amount of the incentive as it is given only once in a life term to girls conditioning that they have to pass Class X examination and also to attain eighteen years of age. Attention will be given to the SC, ST girls, who are considered to be the disadvantaged sections of the society, who have been benefited through this scheme, and also how far this scholarship helps them in getting academic excellence in education. A close look on the performance of the students, who have been awarded the scholarship hopefully will reverberate the schemes well. The study envisages the perspectives of students, heads of the institutions, including teachers, where the students involvement and achievement is found to be more important than any other factor and that perpetuates among the poor children to propel themselves towards reaching the goal of scoring more and also enrolling themselves for higher education, and even to the level of reaching the highest degrees of research.

Specific Objectives of the Study

1. To study the implementation process of the scheme
2. To review the utilisation and achievement pattern by different States/UTs.
3. To assess the impact of financial assistance provided to girl students belongs to Scheduled Castes and economically poor families.
4. To identify the challenges faced in effective implementation of the scheme.

Review of Literature

Udit Agnihotri (2023) highlighted our struggle should begin with a demand for a 'Common School System' that ensures Equality, Equity and Social Justice as a prerequisite to rebuild a new India on the principles and values embodied in the constitution.

Education of girls becomes a priority not only to Government and non-governmental agencies, but also is imminent among educationists, scholars and researchers. Vimala Ramachandran, in her pioneering work, argues that reaching the unreached girls and women are the predominant motive behind the education programmes carried out for girls. A document brought out in 1998 notes that successful community awareness and mobilization campaigns under DPEP have contributed to significant accelerated increase in enrolment, especially of girls. She also attempted an effort to capture the emerging picture with respect to girls' and women's education in India. While the general narrative has a national focus, concrete examples, experiences, case studies and voices from the field have been drawn from Rajasthan. Given the size of India and the enormity of the problem, it is not possible to do justice to a wide range of issues impacting on girls and women's education. Ramachandran focuses attention on policy makers and argues for political will, greater commitment and effective leadership to ensure sincere implementation of government's own policies and programmes for women's education in India.

One of the highly-validated reports of UNESCO says, "There are still 58 million girls worldwide who are not in school. The majority of these girls live in sub-Saharan Africa and South and West Asia. The Millennium Development Goal (MDG) to get as many girls as boys into primary and secondary school by 2005 is likely to be missed in more than 75

countries.” The report further adds, “We need to make much better progress. There is growing international commitment and consensus on what can be done to improve girls’ education...” The report further adds that the right to education is denied to 58 million girls, and a further 45 million boys, even at the primary school level.

Methodology

Any scheme, established by the government, becomes paramount importance when it is implemented for the welfare and improvement of girl students. The study envisages the perspectives of students, parents, heads of the institutions, including teachers, where the student’s involvement and achievement is found to be more important than any other factor and that perpetuates among the poor children to propel themselves towards reaching the goal of scoring more and also enrolling themselves for higher education, and even to the level of reaching the highest degrees of research.

Sampling

Sampling is one of the foremost research tool, which has been instituted for this evaluation. For that purpose, eight States were selected as sample states – Arunachal Pradesh, Bihar, Himachal Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Punjab, Puducherry, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal. These states have been selected so as to cover all the regions of the country – that is, two from the North, one each from the South and the West, one from the East and one among the North-Eastern States. Two specific districts from each of the sample States were identified, for the purpose of the study in consultation with the authorities concerned from the respective States. Similarly, from each district coming under the purview of the study, at least ten schools were selected, with ten students each, selected in turn, for the survey from each of these schools. In analyzing the girl students, their class of study, socio-economic backgrounds, education status of the family members and their perceptions, their annual income, occupation and issues related to NSIGSE scheme were considered and given utmost importance. The head of the institution of a Government or Government-Aided school, and other officials who deal with the scheme at districts and state level were also covered in the analysis for assessing the effectiveness of this incentive scheme.

Overall, there were 16 Districts with at least 219 schools and a selected 1,889 girl students enrolled in class IX during the period 2008-09 to 2011-12 from the selected 8 States were covered for the evaluation of this scheme. The evaluation, which was carried out meticulously, ensured the nature and progress of the scheme, the beneficiaries and other participants, and getting more information from the field, and made the study into an interesting one. The sample schools cover Government, Government-aided and schools run by Local bodies.

Table 1: Names of Sample States and Districts

Sl. No.	State	District
1	Arunachal Pradesh	Papum Pari and Subansiri
2	Bihar	West Champaran and Gaya
3	Himachal Pradesh	Solan and Bilaspur
4	Madhya Pradesh	Bhopal and Baitul
5	Punjab	Fatehgarh Sahib and SBS Nagar
6	Puducherry	Yanam and Karaikkal
7	Tamil Nadu	Erode and Villupuram
8	West Bengal	Nadia and Purulia

Tools Used Field Survey became a significant research method to collect, receive and understand information personally by visiting schools, meeting the officers, heads of institutions, teachers and girl students, who all had a very important role in assessing the experience of the girls, parents and institutions after the implementation of the scheme at the institution level. The field work, which has been carried out in eight states of India, was identified that the states have strong and impinging experiences that the girls belonging to SC, ST and Backward families, have been undergoing tremendous problems and find it difficult to complete the secondary and senior secondary education as proper help and guidance are not given to them.

Questionnaires and schedules become vital in such type of researches for collecting data on the spot. Two different schedules were prepared for the Institution Heads, and officials

which comprised of many questions that included asking information on the knowledge of the scheme NSIGSE, enrolment of the girl students in class IX, academic performance of the girls, difficulties in implementation of the scheme, tracing those girl students who had already passed Class X, completed eighteen years of age, but went a far for higher studies and so on.

**Statistics
Used in the
Study**

Table 2: Year-wise number of girls eligible for incentive and amount sanctioned

(2008-09 to 2012-13)

Year	States/UTs	Total No. Girls	Amount in Crores
2008-09	27	454778	136.435
2009-10	23	404699	121.7835
2010-11	24	507866	152.3214
2011-12	27	474440	142.3318
2012-13	20	235668	70.7004

Source: MHRD, Government of India

Graph 1: Year-wise amount sanctioned (2008-09 to 2012-13)

The above graph exhibits the details of incentive amounts that have been sanctioned over years in the sample states. The data analysis proves that Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Punjab are the best performer as compare to other states. Every year student's application for the incentive is very high as compare to other states. Bihar has only send the application in the year 2008-09. But the number of application has increased over the year in almost every state. Tamil Nadu is the only state which has consistently sending maximum number of application. The maximum number of application shows that the state and concern officials i.e. nodal officer for this scheme and institutions heads are aware about the scheme and their dedication towards benefiting the poor and downtrodden more and more.

Table 3: Allotment of NSIGSE incentives among the Sample States and Union Territories from 2008-09 to 2011-12

Name of State	2008-09		2009-10		2010-11		2011-12		2012-13	
	No of Girls	Amount (Rs in Crore)	No of Girls	Amount (Rs in Crore)	No of Girls	Amount (Rs in Crore)	No of Girls	Amount (Rs in Crore)	No of Girls	Amount (Rs in Crore)
Arunachal Pradesh	2853	0.856	-	-	-	-	2083	0.6249	1370	0.411
Bihar	10366	3.11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Himachal Pradesh	2176	0.653	6233	1.87	7616	2.285	7718	2.315	5991	1.797
Madhya Pradesh	48022	14.407	55177	16.553	56213	16.8639	57504	17.2512	-	-
Punjab	30191	9.057	34524	10.357	41956	12.5868	45301	13.59	41629	12.4887
Puducherry	1526	0.458	1140	0.342	1618	0.485	1689	0.507	1450	0.435
Tamil Nadu	110991	33.297	104967	31.49	114153	34.2462	86414	25.9242	-	-
West Bengal	-	-	-	-	19037	5.7111	12503	3.7509	19449	5.8347

Source: MHRD, Govt. of India

Graph: 2: Allotment of NSIGSE incentive amount among the sample states from 2008-09 to 2012-13

Empirical Evidence from the Field

The field work, which has been carried out in eight states of India exemplifies the process of the implementation of the scheme. The selection of states points out some of the impinging experiences that the girls belonging to SC, ST and Backward families. The data shows that girls belonging to poor and impoverished families undergo tremendous problems and find it difficult to complete the secondary and senior secondary education as proper help and guidance are not given to them. The girls belong to below poverty line families (BPL) have further difficulties in attaining good education.

It has been identified, most of the students, teachers, head masters and district level officers are not aware of the norms of the scheme fully. Officials at the state level are busy with number of State government schemes in secondary education and so, it is obligatory that States are to be motivated to take special interest to implement the scheme at different levels because there are large number of norms and conditions in the scheme. Central and State Government should organize awareness campaigns at different level from time to time; organize meetings, conduct orientation programmes for all the officers and heads of the institutions to implement the scheme effectively for equipping officials, headmasters, teachers and students.

The survey clearly points out the duration of time between the date of submission and the time of delivery is a big gap, and it has to be reduced. So, it is suggested that the incentive amount to be disbursed immediately after the passing of Class

X. It has been observed that there must be strong communication and coordination needed among MHRD, State nodal office, Core Bank, Bank Branches, district offices and schools. The MHRD, Government of India, may give special instructions to all the banks and post offices to open zero balance savings bank account, and continue the accounts for long duration for the transfer of incentive amount. The student's savings bank account should not be treated like other SB accounts of the general public.

The administrative structure of the various state governments and the central government make some restrictions in the passing of the sanctioning of the incentives. The state government officials have the opinion that the core bank and MHRD are taking too much time for transferring the incentive amount after submitting all the requisite information. For example, both Bihar and Tamil Nadu have been waiting for 2008-09 payments. The MHRD and core bank must speed-up the payment process and set-up a time frame.

The MHRD must create a provision to upload the details in its web portal and give directions to all the schools and students to upload their particulars / information in the NSIGSE web portal. Most of the States are using web portal for implementing their incentive and scholarship schemes. States like Punjab, Tamil Nadu and Himachal Pradesh included NSIGSE details in their web portal. They are very systematic in collection of data from schools. So, the centre may also follow it.

Since state nodal officers of all the sample states are burdened with filling and feeding of so much data for the NSIGSE scheme, there was also very little communication done between the State Nodal office, the District Education Office and schools. There is no coordination found among the State nodal office, Core Bank, Bank Branches, district offices and schools. It has been suggested that the filling, feeding and processing of the scheme may be minimized and computerized.

Analysis

The analysis of the field study exemplifies some of the most important factors related with girls secondary education, particularly on the NSIGSE incentive scheme and its prominence among them. Negative parental attitudes toward educating daughters can also be a barrier to a girl's education. Many parents view educating sons as an investment because the sons will be responsible for caring for aging parents. The Dalit and Muslim girls are almost likely to be excluded from schools than their counterparts. Disabled children, and among them disabled girls in particular, constitute a significant group that is denied access to education. The leitmotif of the NSIGSE scheme, which has been implemented effectively, has reduced the drop-out rate in Secondary and Senior/Higher Secondary Schools. The scheme has not only received a warm welcome among the poor, depressed and impoverished low-income generation, but also got its importance among the academic-intellectual generation for its merit of raising the unexpected generation, who never desired to send their children to higher classes of schooling, that gives the meritorious students, who really deserve some kind of stipend from the authorities to support their education, is of 'upward mobility' in school education.

Graph 3: Student's having Aadhar Card/Ration Card/ BPL Card

The above graph shows that except Arunachal Pradesh and Bihar in all other states maximum number of student are having both ration card and Aadhar card. Though Arunachal Pradesh is a small State located in the remote North-East corner of India, the importance the State gives, become prominent and the people have the provision of

locating themselves according to their incomes categorically. Whereas, states like Himachal Pradesh and Punjab very less number of students are having BPL card. This shows that there is a kind of discrepancy in the way of issuing BPL and Aadhar Cards. The pivotal role what is played by the oppressed sections of the society and the impacts of the educational chances given to them on the background of the poverty and illiteracy propels the people to enhance their academic and personal attitude to have better lives in almost every part of India.

It is also to be noted here that the States, which have been considered to be average and below average in their standards and benefits to their people, must come out with some new policies for setting new standards while undergoing the path of progress. When the people improve, there could be a possibility of even other states and regions, which will become accessible to the new forms of facilities may also get improved.

Graph 4: Improvement in Academic Performance

The incentive scheme is found to be a vitalizing agent as it motivates millions of girls from the poor and depressed families to do higher education and come up in their lives. 56.5% (1067/1889) of girls responded that they were motivated to go for higher education, and also declared that they have been getting some kind of help from this incentive scheme. More than 75 % (118/156) of the Headmasters and teachers also acknowledged that the incentive awardees are really motivated and doing better in their studies. The teachers were of the opinion that the attendance of the incentive awardees had been drastically and tremendously increased and they were really performing well in their studies.

Drop-out and Attendance

The immaculate response of the girls clearly says that a great amount of people favored that the attendance is growing up and drop-out rate is decreasing. The idea of progressive and improving attendance is generated and systematized properly with the help of new scholarships and incentives. Ever since the incentive schemes are introduced by the Government of India, the underprivileged sections felt the advantageous part and moved into utilizing the opportunities at the best possible way.

Table4: Improvement in Girls Attendance and Dropout

State	Improvement attendance			Total
	Yes	No	Can't Say/no incentive received	
Arunachal Pradesh	6	4	2	12
	50.0%	33.3%	16.7%	100.0%
Bihar	16	2	0	18
	88.9%	11.1%	0.0%	100.0%
Himachal Pradesh	15	5	1	21
	71.4%	23.8%	4.8%	100.0%
Madhya Pradesh	31	4	2	37
	83.8%	10.8%	5.4%	100.0%
Puducherry	15	2	1	18
	83.3%	11.1%	5.6%	100.0%
Punjab	9	1	0	10
	90.0%	10.0%	0.0%	100.0%
Tamil Nadu	18	0	1	19
	94.7%	0.0%	5.3%	100.0%
West Bengal	14	7	0	21
	66.7%	33.3%	0.0%	100.0%
Total	124	25	7	156
	79.5%	16.0%	4.5%	100.0%

Graph 5: Improvement in Girls Attendance and Drop-out

The graph above shows that the attendance among the girl students has been improved after the implementation of the welfare schemes for girls, particularly those studying in secondary and senior secondary schools. Meanwhile, the data points out the fact that most of the recipients of the awards responded that the drop-out rate among girl students has been drastically reduced. This attitude of girl students, particularly their parents, who are whole-heartedly interested to send them to school and other institutions for education proves to be upward educational progress among the marginalised people.

Incentive Amount

Though the NSIGSE scheme has been found an important one among the girls, it has its impediments also, particularly on the incentive amount, which is comparatively less. The field data proves that the amount is indiscriminately less and essentially improved for making the scheme better.

Graph 6: Desired Incentive amount by the respondents

The above graph categorically points out most of the girls prefer to have the amount to be increased. While some of them preferred Rs.15000/- and above, most of the respondents preferred to have between Rs. 5000/- to Rs.10000/-. The data shows that the desirable amount to be bestowed on to the girls be fixed at Rs. 10000/-. Here also some of the progressive states like Tamil Nadu and Himachal Pradesh, which are almost contended with the amount regarding the increment, where as West Bengal, Madhya Pradesh and so on have a tendency of making the things happen through an enhancement in the amount of the incentive.

Table 5: State-wise sample head master's opinion on incentive amount

State	Amount Sufficient		Total	Suggest Amount				Total
	Yes	No		Rs 5000	Rs. 10000	Rs. 20000	Not Applicable	
Arunachal Pradesh	0	12	12	2	9	1	0	12
	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%	16.7%	75.0%	8.3%	0.0%	100.0%
Bihar	4	14	18	9	4	3	2	18
	22.2%	77.8%	100.0%	50.0%	22.2%	16.7%	11.1%	100.0%
Himachal Pradesh	9	12	21	5	7	2	7	21
	42.9%	57.1%	100.0%	23.8%	33.3%	9.5%	33.3%	100.0%
Madhya Pradesh	15	22	37	18	5	0	14	37
	40.5%	59.5%	100.0%	48.6%	13.5%	0.0%	37.8%	100.0%
Puducherry	1	17	18	8	7	2	1	18
	5.6%	94.4%	100.0%	44.4%	38.9%	11.1%	5.6%	100.0%
Punjab	4	6	10	2	0	2	6	10
	40.0%	60.0%	100.0%	20.0%	0.0%	20.0%	60.0%	100.0%
Tamil Nadu	3	16	19	16	0	1	2	19
	15.8%	84.2%	100.0%	84.2%	0.0%	5.3%	10.5%	100.0%
West Bengal	0	21	21	7	13	0	1	21
	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%	33.3%	61.9%	0.0%	4.8%	100.0%
Total	36	120	156	67	45	11	33	156
	23.1%	76.9%	100.0%	42.9%	28.8%	7.1%	21.2%	100.0%

The headmasters also suggested the scheme should be useful for the girls provided the incentive amount is increased. The Headmasters, including the teachers also opined that the incentive amount is to be enhanced to Rs. 10000/-. For the response to the schedules, among a total of 156 Headmasters, 120 (76.9%) of them were not in favour of the present amount of Rs. 3000/-. Rather, 45 (28.8%) Headmasters responded that the amount must be 10000/-, and some of them demanded in favour of Rs. 20000/-. In Arunachal Pradesh and West Bengal, the entire headmasters favored the amount to be increased into 10000/-; and Punjab where some headmasters were favoring for Rs. 20000/- and even the other sample states also were favoring to increase the amount.

Result and Discussion

The NSIGSE Scheme helped poor families in sending their girl children for Secondary education and, in the process of continuing their higher education. Parents and teachers also recognized the students' potential and talent through the scheme. The scheme acts as a motivation for incentive holders to continue their education and be very clear about their academic goals. The scheme propels the poor girls not only to enhance the academic merits during the school years but also gives competitive spirit among the students that prompts many among them to aspire for higher education and in pursuit of better careers. This also has an inspirational effect on their younger siblings, neighbors and relatives on the academic front. Apart from their inspirational roles, awardees also give constructive guidance to others for applying.

The financial support, through this scheme, enables parents send their children for higher classes particularly professional courses, purchasing books and other stationery items, with some children even saving money from the incentive amount for getting special training for skill development in computers and so on. Students are very conscientious about their studies as well as the need to perform well after being selected for the incentives. Though the awardees seemed to be unhappy to get the incentive amount because it is too low, and also an inordinate delay in getting it credited in to their own accounts.

Heads of all the institutions disclosed that the NSIGSE Scheme has given motivation among girls at the Secondary classes, particularly from classes VIII to X. A marvelous change was discerned among the awardees, which were attending their schools regularly and excelling in their academic performance after knowing the fact that they will be benefitted in the future. For instance, in Punjab, the admission of girls in schools has increased in positive way and on the other hand dropout rate has decreased because a girl child is able to get the monetary incentive to continue her further studies.

Conclusion

Education in India, particularly women's education, has become a vital and most essential part of the progress and development, when the State brings new innovative programmes for helping those girls who are helpless without adequate and essential support at home and school, and it is inevitable the fact that only through education Indian women can be progressed. The marginalized people of India, who used undergo many difficulties in the past, take education as major challenge. The incentives and scholarship schemes, which are introduced by the Government of India, have been making some exhilarating opportunities among these sections. It has been studied that the NSIGSE scheme, which is

implemented effectively, has reduced the drop-out rate in Secondary and Senior/Higher Secondary Schools.

The strongly sympathizing attitude of the people with the State on this 'affirmative action' guaranteed that the students also realize and believe in the equity and democratization of equal opportunities initiated by the State machineries and its implementation as well as implications. The underprivileged sections of our society, which have been passing through under tremendous implications of inability and infringements to send their girls for schooling will get a boost up through this scholarship and also their children will be benefitted by getting proper systematic education from the childhood, so that it will make some indelible imprints in the annals of Indian education.

It has been identified that the incentive programme for girls, National Scheme on Incentives for Girls Secondary Education (NSIGSE) not only helps the girls from the most depressed sections to enroll themselves in schools for reaching secondary education, but also benefits the poor illiterate parents eagerly seeing their girl children to attain education at a good level.

Even though the incentive programme is a heart-warming for the girls who have been studying in secondary and senior secondary schools, the process of implementation of the scholarship seemed to be mind-boggling. The scheme also brings some impediments often in the process of sanctioning and disbursement as the amount is to be given to the girl only on the attainment of eighteen years and passing of Class X. The underprivileged sections of our society, which have been passing through under tremendous implications of inability and infringements to send their girls for schooling will get a boost up through this scholarship and also their children will be benefitted by getting proper systematic education from the childhood, so that it will make a new history in the annals of Indian education.

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